

General English Textbooks of Osmania University at U.G. Level – A Study Based on Michel Byram’s Content Analysis

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Abstract:

The ELT scene is incomplete without the role, design and purposefulness of the textbooks prescribed. This calls for evaluation of the textbooks to investigate their orientation and allegiance. An analysis of the Osmania University General English Curriculum prescribed for under graduate courses of B.A., B.Sc., B.Com., B.B.A. is carried out both quantitatively and qualitatively to arrive at a conclusion about their content.

Key Words: Patterns of culture, Second language acquisition, data coding, contextual language learning, task based syllabus.

I. Introduction

The present paper contains the methodology of the research, instruments applied for the purpose of research and the data of the survey of the English textbooks of General English at the Osmania University for the B.A., B.Sc., and B.Com. courses in 2016-17. The aims of language teaching, the functions of a textbook and its role in the language learning process are also examined.

The check-list for review of the contents in the college level English textbooks is based on the principle of Second Language Acquisition and the factors that impede learning due to cultural alienation.

The relevant data is analysed, presented statistically and examined qualitatively with appropriate examples from the texts. The quantitative analysis is in the form of a table based on patterns of culture. The resultant data is evaluated by the research design aimed at answering research questions based on the frequency of the cultural content and the manner in which the content is presented. This paper examines the ways in which culture finds its reflection in the ESL textbooks. The hypothesis that “cultural alienation causes ineffective learning” is also tested. The check-list of evaluation for cultural content compiled by Michael Byram¹, the five categories of patterns of culture are the research tools employed to test the hypothesis.

II. Role of a Textbook in Language Learning

A textbook has various levels in a minimal framework of analysis. It is a teacher as it contains the needed material to teach. It is a path that gives directions to the teacher and students about the areas to be explored and the way ahead. It is a guide to the route taken in the academic year so far. Though most of the learners and some teachers believe that a textbook needs to be completely “done” from cover to cover, it is in fact a context. It is a resource that has appropriate material which may or may not be used. It is also a context as it initiates discussions and supplements the learning process. It is by itself insufficient in terms of including everything that is expected to be learnt. It serves as a teacher-trainer too for untrained or new teachers. The teacher-notes and explanations with step-by-step teaching plan helps the teachers. The instructions and guidance also serve to maintain uniformity in all the classes at the given level. Thus, a text book could be a supervisor that is written and compiled by language experts and a reliable, valid authority. Some teachers may become dependent on the textbook prescribed instructions without using creativity and enterprise. The textbook, then, becomes a “de-skinner”² where, the teacher goes over the content without engaging with it interactively. Finally, a textbook can be viewed as an ideology. It is a reflection of the culture systems and social parameters that may be indirectly imposed on the teaching environment. It indirectly controls and moulds the view of the culture. This cultural aspect usually remains unrecognised. On a closer inspection, it reveals an underlying perspective which can be visible by asking questions about why and in whose interest the text is made available.

English textbooks most often work to further cultural politics by including or eliminating aspects of political, social, economic and cultural realities.³ The cultural content is influenced possibly due to the place of origin of the text, views of the decision making body and commercial compulsions.

The efforts in the newly born countries to produce text books on their own shows how there is a change in the political and social thinking to view textbooks as cultural commodities. The textbooks for transmission of cultural framework are no longer accepted whole-heartedly in the countries which are in the expanding ELT circle. Designers and evaluators of textbooks are now encouraged to evaluate the EFL / ESL textbooks against the requirements prescribed in the evaluation check-lists.

III. Use of Check-list for Evaluation

The use of “off the shelves” check-lists may not be suitable or reliable for a comprehensive evaluation. It is hence imperative to make modifications to the existing one or design an entirely new check-list to accommodate individual needs because “global list of criteria can never really apply in most local environments without considerable modifications.”⁴ A thorough list of criteria for the evaluation of the textbook is Michael Byram’s list that throws light on cultural content. Such criteria and evaluation studies are appropriate in a defined region such as Telangana State in the present case.

IV. Michael Byram's Check-list for Cultural Evaluation

Michael Byram's list for textbook evaluation has focus on cultural content. It consists of 8 categories and the categories are further subdivided.⁵ The extent of focus on each of the cultural contents is depicted below.

1. <i>Social identity and social group.</i> It includes groups within a country or state that are the basis for their identity other than national identity. It includes social Class, regional identity, ethnic minority that demonstrates complex individual social identity.
2. <i>Social interaction.</i> It includes routines, accepted social behaviour in interactions within a social group at different levels of formality.
3. <i>Belief and behaviour.</i> It includes daily conventional actions within social settings. It also consists of religious and moral beliefs.
4. <i>Social and political institutions.</i> It consists of states, healthcare, law and order, social security, local government and business and industry.
5. <i>Socialization and life cycle.</i> It includes family, school, employment, ceremonies and sports . Media, food and folklore have been included to make categorization exhaustive.
6. <i>National history.</i> It includes historical events seen as markers of national identity.
7. <i>National geography.</i> It includes factors that are viewed as significant by the members.
8. <i>Stereotype and national identity.</i> It includes what is a symbol of national identity or typical stereotype; example, famous people or monuments.

Figure 1

V The Patterns of Culture

Five patterns reflect culture in the English language textbooks.

The first pattern is host culture (HC) or culture of Indian sub-continent.

The second pattern is the use of L₁ culture (TC) or culture from the L₁ speaking countries like Britain, Australia and North America.

The third pattern is the use of other cultures that are neither a source culture nor a L₁ culture; these are cultures in various countries both L₁ speaking and non-L₁ speaking around the world who use English as an International Language (EIL); this is also called International Culture (IC).

The fourth pattern is inter-cultural interaction (ICI). It includes the comparison, reflection or awareness of the differences and similarities between the host culture and the L₁ or international culture (IC).

Universality across cultures (UaC) is the fifth pattern. It includes general knowledge or content that is not specific to any particular culture or country.

VI. Data Collection and Analysis

The recording units are contents of prose passages and poetry pieces. L1 Cultural content will be collected, coded under the eight categories and their respective 28 sub-categories that are found in Byram's check-list.

Present evaluative research examines and analyses the contents of textbook for cultural affinity. In addition to this qualitative research method, quantitative method is also used in the form of tables, bar graphs, frequencies and percentages. The data has been coded manually and examined for evaluation according to the frequency of occurrence in the text. Responses to the questionnaire that contains objective and analytical questions are also presented. The present study may be considered a mixed method research as some elements of both qualitative and quantitative research are applied for data analysis. After the data coding was complete, the frequencies of certain levels were checked and final conclusions were drawn. The overview of the English textbooks from the Undergraduate English textbooks prescribed by the Telangana State under the jurisdiction of Osmania University is also included.

VII. Overview of the Undergraduate Course Textbooks of Osmania University Curriculum

The non-professional courses at the Undergraduate level (B.A., B.Com. and B.Sc.) of Osmania University are three year courses. English is prescribed for the initial two years. The English component of the Undergraduate course consists of General Purpose English (G.P.E.) course which is made up of selections from prose, poetry and short stories.

The preface of the First Year textbook *English Made Easy* begins by acknowledging that English has come to the centre-stage of global communication. It further states that to succeed in professional and personal lives, all educated youngsters must learn good English. The courses in English, the preface says, are being designed keeping the real-life, contextual aspects of language, in mind through a task-based syllabus. It includes four genres – short fiction, prose, poetry and drama - as the starting point of the contextual language learning.

It also mentions that the materials development team and the editors have ensured that the learners evolve to be proficient English users. It is significant that no mention is made of the cultural or global input necessary to make English learning effectively inter-cultural and intra-cultural.

The *Advanced Skills in English*, Second Year Undergraduate textbook's preface starts with a mention about the current global trend in the teaching of communication skills towards developing an all-round skills set. It asserts that Osmania University has been prominent

among the educational institutions of this region in nurturing and promoting education equipped to face the new global scenario.

Quantitative Data containing L1 Culture Content in Undergraduate Curriculum of Osmania University

Class	Ist Year	IInd Year	Total	
No. of units	8	12	20	
1. Social Identity and Social Group				
• Social Class	1	1	2	2
• Regional Identity				
• Ethnic Minority				
2. Social Interaction				
• Differing Levels of Formality		1	1	1
• Greeting				
• Non Verbal Language				
3. Belief and Behaviour				
• Moral, Religious Belief		1		1
• Daily Routines				
4. Social and Political Institutions				
• State				1
• Health care	1		1	
• Law and order				
• Social security				
• Local government				
• Business and industry				
5. Socialization and Life Cycle				
• Family				2
• School				
• Employment				
• Media				
• Ceremonies				
• Sports/Adventure				
• Folklore		2	2	
• Food				
6. National History				
• Historical events seen as makers of national identity				1
• Contemporary events seen as markers of national identity				
7. National Geography				
• Geographic factors seen as being significant by members	1		1	1

8. Stereo Types and National Identity				
• What is typical symbols of national identity				2
• Famous people		2	2	
• Famous monuments				
Total	3	7		10
Class wise percentage of L₁ Culture (%)	30	70		100

Fig. 2

The curriculum of the Undergraduate course textbooks of Osmania University is presented on the basis of the patterns of culture in the Figure3.

Figure 3

Distribution of lessons in undergraduate course books of Osmania University

Distribution of Units in Undergraduate Curriculum of Osmania University

Class	HC	TC	IC	ICI	UaC	Total
Ist Year	1	3	2	-	2	8
IInd Year	3	7	1	-	1	12
Total	4	10	3	-	3	20
Percentage	20%	50%	15%	-	15%	100%

Figure 4

VIII. Analysis of L₁ Culture in Undergraduate Curriculum of Osmania University

Category Sub-Category	1. Social Identity and Social Group				
	Units Identified	Class	Name of the lesson	Author	Country

Social Class	2	II Yr.	Open Window	Hector Hugh Munro	U.K
		I Yr.	A visit to charity	Eudora Welty	U.S

Category		2. Social Interaction			
Sub-Category	Units Identified	Class	Name of the lesson	Author	Country
Differing Levels of Formality	1	II Yr.	Uncle Podger Hangs a Picture	Jerome K. Jerome	U.K
Category		3. Belief and Behaviour			
Sub-Category	Units Identified	Class	Name of the lesson	Author	Country
Moral, Religious Belief	2	I Yr.	Happy People	William Ralph Inge	U.K
		I Yr.	The Dear Departed	Stanley Houghton	U.K

Category		4. Social and Political Institutions			
Sub-Category	Units Identified	Class	Name of the lesson	Author	Country
Health Care	1	I Yr.	The Curb in the Sky	James Thurber	U.S

Category		5. Socialization and Life Cycle			
Sub-Category	Units Identified	Class	Name of the lesson	Author	Country
Folklore	2	II Yr.	Father William	Lewis Carol	U.K
		II Yr.	The Table and the Chair	Edward Lee	U.K
Category		7. National Geography			
Sub-Category	Units Identified	Class	Name of the lesson	Author	Country
Geography Factors seen as being significant by members	1	I Yr.	Stanzas Written in Dejection Near Naples	P.B Shelley	U.K

Category		8. Stereotypes and National Identity			
Sub-Category	Units Identified	Class	Name of the lesson	Author	Country
Famous People	2	II Yr.	Larry Page and Sergey Brian	Larry Page and Sergey Brian	U.S

		II Yr.	Martin Luther King	---	U.S
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Figure 5

IX. Undergraduate Level English Textbooks of Osmania University

It is surprising that the Ist Year textbook has no units based on local Culture. All units have L₁ writers. The exception being *Benaras* that is, by Aldous Huxley. Though the content is native, the approach, tone and opinion of the writer make the essay unpalatable. The description of the ghats of Ganges on “the day of solar eclipse”, “the stagnating water”, “holy men contemplating the brown and sweating tips of their noses”, and “sacred slime” are examples of his derisive tone. The linguistic dimension at semantic level is missing in the text. It does cater to the need to discover what unites human beings, with a focus on commonality and bonds of religion.

The L₁ culture is excessively present in the form of short story *The Curb in the Sky*, drama *Julius Caesar*, *The Dear Departed*, short fiction *Visit of Charity* and poem by PB Shelley. These above mentioned units are not found to be consistent with the psychological and linguistic abilities of the learners. They fail to match the vocabulary and syntax because of differences in culture of L₁ language and L₂ language. In the Second Year English textbook, *Larry Page and Sergey Brin*, *Martin Luther King*, and *The Open Window* represent L₁ culture. All three poetry pieces are L₁ culture specific. *The Table and the Chair*, for instance, was written by Edward Lear for the grand children of the Earl of Derby. The poems do not simulate real-life situations and the predominant use of Western and urban spoken models do not suit curriculum of Host Culture learners. Such content fails to evoke feeling of familiarity and belongingness. The characters of L₁ culture specific content embody alien values, which leads to students performing acts that are considered taboos socially and culturally.

The students are misled into believing that the linguistic phrases learnt through these textbooks will be appropriate in scenario described in the unit; but it is highly unlikely in reality.

The students from vernacular medium do not have skills and understanding that is necessary for effective interpretation of conversational implicatures in English. Even those from English medium schools have little knowledge about how implicatures work, how implicatures function as tools for indirect communication, and how various types of implicatures fit appropriately in a context. Another hurdle is caused by conceptual misunderstanding. The lexical and metaphorical conceptual frameworks of L₁ users are different from the native, local concepts; and hence, the L₂ students fail to manifest the association.

X. Conclusion

Many of the text book designers have not relied on the principles of Second Language Acquisition (SLA) while writing the materials; others, instead, depend on their beliefs and intuitions about what is best for language learning.⁶ This results in a cultural gap that is noticed between the content of the textbooks and the needs of the ESL learner.

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